

The Determination of Slippage of Drifters and the Leeway
of Search and Rescue Targets using InterOcean S4 EMCM

Arthur A. Allen
U.S. Coast Guard
Research and Development Center
Groton, CT 06340-6096

Abstract - The U.S. Coast Guard Research and Development Center, Improvement of Search and Rescue Capabilities Project has conducted studies of the motion of Lagrangian drifters and search and rescue (SAR) targets relative to the water. This slippage was measured using InterOcean S4 electromagnetic current meters (EMCM), and related to measured winds. The slippage of a FGGE Hull drifter (12 days of slippage data in the Labrador Current) was measured with EMCMs attach above and below the window shade drogue. Preliminary studies have been conducted on a WOCE mixed layer drifter (61.6 hours of slippage data) and a CODE surface drifter (37.4 hours of slippage data). All slippage records show considerable high frequency variability. The FGGE drifter had a slippage of 5 cm/s in 10 m/s wind. The WOCE drifter had slippage of 2 cm/s in 10 m/s of wind. The CODE drifter had a slippage of 0.5 cm/s in 5 m/s of wind.

Canadian/US Coast Guard have used EMCM to directly measure the leeway of various SAR targets in winds up to 18 m/s. The SAR targets studied have included 5 and 20 man life rafts, drouged and undrouged, with light and heavy loadings; 5.6 m plank boat, L1011 slide raft, and a enclosed life capsule. Results are currently being assimilated.

I. INTRODUCTION

Satellite tracked drifting buoys have been used by the U.S. Coast Guard for predicting the drift of various objects in the oceans. The U.S. Coast Guard, International Ice Patrol (IIP) has broadcasted to mariners the limits of sea ice and icebergs in the western North Atlantic region each spring and summer since 1914.

IIP estimates the sea ice and iceberg limits based upon overflights combined with a numerical model of iceberg drift with currents that are updated using mixed layer drifters. The First GARP (Global Atmospheric Research Project) Global Experiment (FGGE) drifters are basically a spar buoy with a conical flotation collar attached by 50 m of 1 cm nylon line to a two by ten meter window-shade drogue. The International Ice Patrol has used Argos tracked FGGE drifters to monitor the Labrador Current during 12 iceberg seasons. IIP has recently replaced the large, expensive FGGE drifters with the World Ocean Circulation Experiment (WOCE) drifters. The WOCE drifter is basically a 35 cm spherical surface float that houses the electronics, a tether to a subsurface sphere, and another tether to a 6.5 m holey sock drogue centered at 15 m depth. IIP has modified this design to center the drogue at 50 m depth. To maintain compatibility between the drifter data sets, a comparison of the errors of the drifters was conducted following the methods of [1] and [2].

The U.S. Coast Guard also conducts about 5000 searches each year of which about 500 are longer than 12 hours. Critical to the successful location of the survivors and their crafts is the estimation of the total displacement of the survivors from the last known position. The prediction of total displacement is based on the estimate the surface currents and the leeway of the survivor crafts due to wind and waves. The Coast Guard is using a modification of Coastal Dynamics Experiment (CODE) drifter developed by [3] to provide on scene near surface current information for search and rescue operations. The Coast Guard CODE drifter are packaged for air deployment from Coast Guard

fixed and rotary wind aircraft. The height of drag vanes was reduced from 1.0 m to 0.7 m. The width of the drifter was maintained at 1.0 m. The result is a 7/10th scaled CODE drifter. The drag vanes were between 0.3 m and 1.0 m depth. This depth range is matched to the leeway studies of SAR targets.

The slippage through the water of Search and Rescue (SAR) targets due to wind is their leeway. The U.S. and Canadian Coast Guards have been conducting joint studies of leeway of various SAR targets off Newfoundland. The SAR targets studied have included 5 and 20 man life rafts, drogued and undrogued, with light and heavy loadings; a 5.6 m wooden planked boat; a L1011 slide raft; an enclosed life capsule; a Cuban refugee raft, with and without a sail; and a 15 m commercial fishing vessel with a rear-reel for net fishing.

The slippage through the water of two mixed-layer drifters designs and one surface drifter and the leeway of various SAR targets has been studied by a series of field tests using InterOcean S4 Electromagnetic Current Meters (EMCMs).

The descriptions of sampling methods used for the field work and calibration techniques are presented in section II. Section III summarizes the results. Complete results for the slippage of FGGE drifters are presented in [4] and summarized in section III. Preliminary results for the WOCE drifter are presented in section III. Results of the first two field studies of the surface drifters are present in [5] and summarized in section III. Complete results of the leeway studies (except the Cuban refugee raft and 15 m commercial fishing vessel) are in [5] and [6]. Section IV presents our intended upcoming work.

II. METHODS

1) *Introduction* - The sampling techniques evolved over the course of the field experiments. The sampling schemes were a compromise between the memory and battery limitation of S4 EMCMs based on the anticipated deployment period, and a safety margin. Initially the high frequency motions (near wave frequencies) of

the drifters was investigated before the longer sampling periods were conducted. Subsequently, upgrades in memory, the addition of tilt sensors, and changing from alkaline to lithium batteries, allowed for longer deployments.

2) *Sampling Techniques for the FGGE Drifters* - Three separate field studies were conducted in June 1990 and May 1991. In June 1991 the two deployments were in the Labrador Current and on the Grand Banks. The May 1991 deployment was in the Labrador Current for a total of 12 days of sampling. For each deployment and array of FGGE drifters (one instrumented with two EMCMs, and two uninstrumented) were deployed about a drifting Coastal Climate MiniMet buoy that also had a window shade drogue. The MiniMet buoy sampled winds for 10 minutes every 30 minutes and waves for 20 minutes every 60 minutes. During each field study, the FGGE drifter with the two S4 EMCMs was recovered to download the data and reset the sampling scheme. Several sampling schemes were used to investigate the responses of the drifter to wind and waves. High frequency sampling and recording (1 Hz for 2 minutes every 30 minutes) scheme was used to examine the behavior at wave periods. Available memory limited deployments of ten hours or less. Longer deployment (2 days) necessitated using longer averaging periods and the S4 sampling was set to match the MiniMet.

3) *Sampling Techniques for the WOCE Drifters* - During December 1993 sixty hours of slippage data were collected on a WOCE drifter. The work was conducted on the Grand Banks of Newfoundland in conjunction with a leeway study. InterOcean S4 EMCMs were attached to the mooring line above (11.4 m depth) and below (19.8 m depth) the 6.5 m drogue, Fig.1.

The buoyancy of the WOCE drifter was adjusted to compensate for the extra weight of the two S4 EMCMs. A short length of chain was attached to the lower S4 to stabilize it and to adjust the final buoyancy of the WOCE drifter. The instrumented WOCE drifter was submerged 30% of time compared to the 5-10% for 15 m WOCE drifter and 10-20% for IIP's 50 m WOCE drifters.

Wind data were collected from a drifting leeway 5.6 m open boat that was within 100 km of the WOCE drifter. Wind data were continuous ten minute vector averages of the 3 meter wind, adjusted for the drift of the boat. The EMCMS measurements were also continuous ten minute vector averages.

4) *Sampling Techniques for the CODE Drifters* - The Coast Guard R&D Center along with the National Data Buoy Center (NDBC) has conducted three preliminary field studies to calibrate surface drifters, including the 7/10th CODE drifter. Both indirect and direct methods were employed to determine the slippage of surface drifters. The indirect method used dye sources aboard the drifters to tag a parcel of water. Aerial photography was used to measure the relative displacement and to estimate the horizontal diffusion of the dye plumes. The direct method used a S4 EMCM into the hull of a 7/10th CODE drifter, Fig.2. NDBC tested the indirect method on 14 January 1994 in central northeast Gulf of Mexico. This test was on four surface drifters of Seimac Limited's design. The Seimac Limited surface drifter is a small spar buoy with four arms that float at the surface with triangle vanes alongside the hull. A parachute below the buoy is suspended from the ends of four arms and provides vertical damping for the drifter. The dye source from each Seimac surface drifter produced an continuous plume.

For the second test near Key West Florida, the dye was pumped at 2.5 minute intervals from four 7/10th CODE drifters and aerial photographs were taken at 5 minute intervals. During the sampling period of indirect method, the direct method was used for 55 minutes at a 1 Hz vector averaging rate. The third field test of 7/10th CODE drifters was conducted 25 Oct. to 3 Nov. 1994 of Fort Pierce, FL. The direct method was used to collect data on the slippage of the CODE drifter with four different float shapes: spheres, cylinders, cubes, and discs. The S4 EMCM recorded 1 minute vector averages during this test. 20.1 hours of record was obtained on the CODE drifters with spheres, and 5.5 hours on each of the other float configurations. The drifters were within 5 km of a MiniMet buoy during this field test.

5) *Sampling Techniques for the Leeway Studies -*

The U.S. and Canadian Coast Guard conducted leeway studies in Newfoundland waters during the summer and fall of 1992 and 1993. For each of 56 leeway runs, the SAR target contained the following systems: positioning, tracking, wind monitoring, and a tethered S4 EMCM.

The S4 EMCMs were suspended within a frame at 0.74 meters depth. The S4 frame was attached to a float sized to match the drift of the life rafts. The frame was attached by 15 m line to the pivot point or sea drogue point of the SAR target. Fig.3 is the arrangement used for the 5.6 m wooden plank boat.

For the leeway studies 10 minute vector averages of wind and leeway were sampled. The cosine compensation was applied at 2 Hz to the S4 EMCMs horizontal velocities from the vertical tilt angle. Wind speed and direction were sampled on board the SAR targets at 1 Hz and vector averaged for over ten minutes sampling periods. Compass heading of the SAR target and relative bearing of the wind direction to the SAR target were also recorded. NavStar Global Positioning System (GPS) positions of the SAR targets were recorded every 5 minutes.

6) *Calibrations -* The S4 current meters were calibrated yearly at InterOcean. An attempt was made by Oceans Limited to calibrate the S4 in the National Research Council Canada Institute for Marine Dynamics 200 meter long, 12 meter wide, 7 meter deep tow tank in St John's Newfoundland. Excessive electromagnetic fields generated by nearby electric motors produce interference in the S4 EMCMs.

The wind was measured with R. M. Young anemometers. An aluminum indexed rotating table was used for swinging the anemometers and compasses for the MiniMet buoy and the wind monitoring systems. An open site at the end of Avery Point on the grounds of the Coast Guard R. and D. Center was surveyed to established absolute bearing to permanent distance landmarks. This site is free from buildings and cars, and has a level concrete slab for mounting the table. From this site deviations of compasses and relative bearing of the anemometers as a function of

Fig 3. 5.6m Wooden Plank Boat with S4 EMCM

heading were determined for the MiniMet buoys and the wind monitoring systems. The deviations of S4 EMCMS compasses were determined to be less than 2 degrees. Compass deviations coefficients were entered and applied at sampling rate to wind monitoring systems. Relative wind heading deviations were post-applied to the 10 minute samples. In general most of the offsets (up to 5 degrees) were generated at the A/D conversion and not by raw voltage levels from the sensor. During these experiments we upgraded, the wind and current measuring systems and improved the calibration techniques, however, a simple effective calibration for the S4 EMCMS eludes us.

III. RESULTS

1) Mixed Layer Drifters -

The slippage of a FGGE buoy with a 2 by 10 meter window shade drogue is presented in [3] for wind speeds at 3 meter height from 0 to 10 m/s and wave heights up to 3.5 meters. A linear model of slippage based on wind alone explained 60 percent of the observed variance. The best estimate of the slippage at 10 m/s wind speed was 0.06 m/s [3]. The multiple regression model based on wind and shear across the drogue explained 65 percent of the observed variance [3] is:

$$u = c_1 + c_2 w + c_3 s \quad (1)$$

where u is the slip velocity component (cm/s), w is the wind component (cm/s), and s is the vertical shear (1/s). In (1), units for c_1 are (cm/s), c_2 is dimensionless and c_3 is cm. Table 1 contains the coefficients for this model for both FGGE and WOCE drifters.

TABLE 1
Coefficients to (1)

Drifter	c_1	c_2	c_3
FGGE	0.2	0.0047	950
WOCE	0.02	0.0009	370

The mean slippage of the WOCE drifter over the sampling period (61.6 hours) was 1.7 cm/s with a standard deviation of 0.8 cm/s. The 3 meter wind speeds decrease from 12 m/s to 0 m/s during the sampling period.

As with the FGGE drifters, the slippage of the WOCE drifter showed considerable high frequency variability. Following [3], the auto-correlation scale for the slippage was estimated to be between 0.5 and 3.5 hours. The time series were then averaged over 3 hours which provided 20 independent samples for each slip component. The multiple-linear regression of slippage on winds and shear explained 76 percent of the variance in the slippage record.

2) Surface Layer Drifters

Results of the first two field studies of the surface drifters are present in [5]. During the 24 May 1994 test the direct method was also used. The slippage as measured by the EMCMS averaged over the entire 55 minute sampling period was 0.6 cm/s to the south with of 5.3 m/s winds from the ENE. However, over the sampling period five reversals in slippage direction occurred. These rotations and reversals may be true rotations due the drifter passing through a local front, or false reversals due to rotation of the drifter about its vertical axis.

Additional field testing using the direct S4 EMCMS method has been conducted off Ft. Pierce, FL between 25 Oct. and 3 Nov. 1994 to investigate the effect of float design on the slippage of CODE drifter. The floats tested were spheres, cylinders, discs, and cubes. This data set is now being analyzed.

3) Leeway Studies

Complete leeway equations for leeway as function of wind speed are presented in [6] and [7]. Leeway values for the Cuban refugee raft and commercial fishing vessel are being analyzed. The leeway determined by these studies are lower in speed and contained less divergence from the downwind direction than the values published in the National SAR manual

[8]. In [6] a refined definition of leeway was used that reference leeway to winds adjusted to the 10 m height and sea currents between the 0.3 m to 1.0 m. This is the rationale for the reduction of the CODE drifter to 7/10 size. The divergence from the downwind direction of the SAR targets was considerable less than the plus or minus 35 degrees used by [8]. The crosswind components of leeway are near zero until a threshold wind speed is obtained and then linear increase with wind speed. For single SAR object drift, the divergence can be either left or right of wind. During the 55 runs, only one jibe was observed from left to right of wind. This change occurred during high but steady wind conditions. A breaking wave might have reorientated the 4 man raft and caused the jibe.

V. FUTURE STUDIES

Further work is planned for CODE drifters. We have plans to conduct tow tank calibrations of the S4 EMCM within the CODE drifter as a system. We also conduct a test where the S4 EMCM will be slowly rotated (about 1 revolutions per minute) about its vertical axis to determine if the S4 EMCM records an apparent horizontal current. We will use a system of weights and pulleys to mechanical tow the S4 EMCM at low speeds (1-5 cm/s).

Leeway studies are continuing. Other SAR target of from the mid to larger size will be studied using the present technique. Smaller SAR targets such as person-in-the-water (PIWs), PIW in survival suits, sail boards, 55 gallon drums will require modification to the present techniques.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The efforts of Jim O'Donnell, Reg Fitzgerald, Duncan Finlayson, Neil Van de Voorde Don Murphy in the field and analysis are greatly appreciated. This work has received strong support from Dave Paskausky, Quincy Robe, Tony Patterson and Peter Niiler. Gary Reas and Chris Oates have kept all my instruments in working order.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Niiler, R. Davis, and H. White, 1987. "Water-following characteristics of a mixed layer drifter." Deep Sea Res. 34, 1876-1881.
- [2] W. Geyer, 1989. "Field calibrations of mixed-layer drifter." J. Atmos. and Oceanic Tech. 6, 333-342.
- [3] R. Davis, 1985. "Drifter Observations of Coastal Surface Currents During CODE: The Method and Descriptive View." J. Geoph. Res. 90 4741-4755.
- [4] J. O'Donnell, A. Allen, and D. Murphy, "An Assessment of the Errors in Lagrangian Velocity Estimates Obtained by FGGE Drifters in the Labrador Current" unpublished.
- [5] N. Van de Voorde, "Calibration Techniques for Surface Drifting Buoys" National Data Buoy Center report, unpublished.
- [6] R. Fitzgerald, D. Finlayson, J. Cross, and A. Allen, 1993. "Drift of Common Search and Rescue Objects - Phase II." Contract report prepared for Transportation Development Centre, Transport Canada, Montreal, TP# 11673E, 107pp.
- [7] R. Fitzgerald, D. Finlayson, and A. Allen, 1994. "Drift of Common Search and Rescue Objects - Phase III." Contract report prepared for Canadian Coast Guard, Research and Development, Ottawa TP# 12179, 122pp.
- [8] U.S. Coast Guard, Commandant Publication M16112.5A, "National Search and Rescue Manual," Washington, DC. 1 Feb. 1991.